

System of Novel Binomial Coefficients and Series

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Abstract: This paper presents a system of novel binomial coefficients used in the combinatorial geometric series. Also, a theorem is newly introduced in this article. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to compute the multiple summations of a geometric series [1-12], a new idea stimulated his mind to create a new type of geometric series. As a result, a combinatorial geometric series [11-20] was developed with new idea of binomial coefficients.

2. System of Binomial Coefficients

The combinatorial geometric series is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial geometric series [17-33] refers to the binomial coefficient [29-40].

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \dots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i,$$

$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ denotes the combinatorial geometric series and V_n^r the binomial coefficient.

$N = \{V_0^1, V_1^1, V_2^1, V_3^1, V_4^1, V_4^1, \dots\}$ is a set of natural numbers or system of binomial coefficients.

Let us show that V_n^r belongs to the set of natural numbers, *i. e.* $V_n^r \in N$,

where, $V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\dots(n+r)}{r!}$ and integers $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$.

$V_0^1 = 1; V_1^1 = 2; V_2^1 = 3; V_3^1 = 4; V_4^1 = 5; V_5^1 = 6; \dots$

Let $V_n^r = V_{Q-1}^1$, where $Q = V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\dots(n+r)}{r!}$.

$$V_{Q-1}^1 = \frac{(Q-1+1)}{1!} = Q \quad (OR) \quad V_{V_n^r-1}^1 = \frac{(V_n^r-1+1)}{1!} = V_n^r.$$

$\therefore V_n^r$ belongs to the set of natural numbers, *i. e.* $V_n^r \in N$.

Next, $V_n^r < V_n^{r+1} = V_n^r < V_{n+1}^r, (\because V_n^r = V_r^n)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{n+1}^r - V_n^r &= \frac{(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)(n+r+1)}{r!} - \frac{(n+1)(n+2)\cdots(n+r)}{(r-1)!} \\
&= \frac{(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)}{r!} (n+r+1-n-1) = \frac{(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)}{(r-1)!} \\
&\therefore V_{n+1}^r - V_n^r = V_{n+1}^{r-1}.
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem:
$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r+1} x^i = V_0^r \sum_{i=0}^n x^i + V_1^r \sum_{i=1}^n x^i + V_2^r \sum_{i=2}^n x^i + \cdots + V_{n-1}^r \sum_{i=n-1}^n x^i + V_n^r \sum_{i=n}^n x^i.$$

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using the following binomial expansion.

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r+1} x^i = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i + \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^r x^i + \sum_{i=2}^n V_{i-2}^r x^i + \cdots + \sum_{i=n-1}^n V_{i-(n-1)}^r x^i + \sum_{i=n}^n V_{i-n}^r x^i.$$

The binomial expansion on the left-hand side of the equation is further expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i + \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^r x^i + \sum_{i=2}^n V_{i-2}^r x^i + \cdots + \sum_{i=n}^n V_{i-n}^r x^i \\
&= (V_0^r x^0 + V_0^r x^1 + V_0^r x^2 + \cdots + V_0^r x^n) + (V_1^r x^1 + V_1^r x^2 + V_1^r x^2 + \cdots + V_1^r x^n) \\
&\quad + (V_2^r x^2 + V_2^r x^2 + V_2^r x^2 + \cdots + V_2^r x^n) + \cdots + V_n^r x^n.
\end{aligned}$$

Now, it is concluded that

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r+1} x^i = V_0^r \sum_{i=0}^n x^i + V_1^r \sum_{i=1}^n x^i + V_2^r \sum_{i=2}^n x^i + \cdots + V_{n-1}^r \sum_{i=n-1}^n x^i + V_n^r \sum_{i=n}^n x^i.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

3. Conclusion

In this article, a system of binomial coefficients and a theorem were newly introduced using computational technique. This idea can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real world problems.

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